

SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION**Rajabova S.**

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Abstract

This article examines the scientific and technical aspects of innovative development in the field of education. This paper aims to outline the core scientific and technical aspects that are critical to sustaining innovative development in the education sector.

Keywords: *stimulant, technological education, high technologies, efficiency of the educational process, innovation, global collaboration.*

The word “innovation” means the result of creative activity aimed at the development, creation and distribution of new types of products, technologies, and the introduction of new organizational forms.

American scientist Peter Drucker (1909–2005) understood innovation as “the means by which an entrepreneur either creates new resources that bring him wealth or provides existing resources with improved potential for profit”.

Innovative teaching methods are modern approaches that go beyond traditional education. They include new technologies, ideas and concepts that promote critical thinking, creativity, teamwork and self-realization. [1,17]

Innovative teaching methods are not just the introduction of advanced technologies or following the latest trends, but a complete educational methodology based on new teaching strategies that focus on the needs and characteristics of students. These methods allow students to be actively involved in the learning process and encourage interaction with classmates and the teacher. This means a lot of work on the part of students, but unlike traditional teaching, which focuses on the volume of knowledge transferred, innovative methods allow us to understand what students actually learned in the classroom. [1,19]

Innovative educational activity involves changing the pedagogical process and introducing innovations aimed at improving it. Innovations (in English - the introduction of new forms, methods and skills in the field of training, education and science). Innovative activities include motivation, creativity, operational components, and reflection. Innovation in education means solving real problems in a new and simple way to promote equal learning. [3,4]

The 21st century has seen a revolutionary shift in education, fueled by continuous scientific research and rapid technological advancements. Traditional pedagogical methods are evolving to accommodate new learning environments shaped by digital tools, online resources, and artificial intelligence.

In terms of the requirements of the 21st century, while preserving the successes of traditional education,

the application of innovations and new pedagogical technologies should be considered as important conditions for improving the quality of education. For this reason, hundreds of new concepts have entered our education as innovations. Life skills-based education, curriculum, e-school, ICT, distance learning, active and interactive methods, portfolio, Bologna process, synergistic education, constructive education, synergetics in education, etc. are important areas and methods of innovative education, being new concepts of our education. [2]

These innovations are scaled according to the size of the problem. At present, mechanisms for stimulating innovation activities across all areas have been developed and implemented in order to expand and accelerate their use throughout society. The Concept of "Innovation" It would be a great disingenuousness to claim that innovative activity as such originated recently. Innovations are precisely one of the multifaceted, multi-aspect subjects of discussion. This follows from the diverse concept of "education". In this regard, it is relevant to consider the diversity of types of innovations in education.

Innovative activities in education cover various aspects, from modernizing curricula to introducing new technologies. Among them, several key areas are highlighted that contribute to improving the quality of education and creating new opportunities for students and teachers. Scientific and technological advancements have also revolutionized pedagogy.[4,294] If this activity was called so relatively recently, it does not mean that it did not exist and did not bear fruit - innovations, which we call innovations. The wheel and other mechanisms (relevant today) were invented before our era. It would be very incorrect not to consider this as an innovation at that period of human development. One of the effective ways to solve these problems is the informatization of education. [2]

Today, information technologies in education open up a whole range of different innovative directions, among which the most modern is the didactic aspects of information technologies. Thus, we can conclude that education has always worked in an innovative mode to a greater or lesser extent. Improvement of

technical means of communication has led to significant progress in information exchange. The emergence of new information technologies associated with the development of computer technology and telecommunications networks has made it possible to create a qualitatively new information and educational environment as a basis for the development and improvement of the education system. The task of technology as a science is to identify a set of patterns with the aim of determining and using in practice the most effective, consistent educational actions that require less time, material and intellectual resources to achieve any result.

However, let us be as precise and objective as possible: at various stages of development of systems and paradigms of education, several very specific key methodological (technological) approaches to teaching were used: • practice; • material transmission; • analysis and analysis of situations; • game; • imitation; • project. [2]

Materials and Methods: Today, science and education are among the most important factors ensuring the country's sustainable socio-economic and cultural development. In the modern era, the role and importance of education and scientific-technical progress are acknowledged as serious factors.

In recent years, decisions have been made to advance science, protect and modernize scientific-technical potential and intellectual property, train highly qualified personnel in science and education, provide them with constant support, increase the prestige of scholars and educators in society, and promote Azerbaijani scientific achievements abroad. [12] The state's attention to the development of science and education should be considered as part of the broader policy aimed at strengthening statehood and contributing to national-cultural progress and raising the well-being of the people. From this perspective, coordinating the fields of science and education, integrating them with the use of modern technologies and innovations, and their development remains a top priority issue. Several key technologies have significantly influenced modern education systems. Cloud computing provides scalable and remote access to educational tools, allowing for global collaboration. With the expansion of the Internet of Things, smart classrooms are being developed to enhance interactivity, track student engagement, and provide immediate feedback. [12]

Gamification of learning—using game elements such as rewards, levels, and challenges—has proven effective in increasing motivation and engagement. STEM and STEAM education encourage interdisciplinary learning, combining science, technology, engineering, mathematics and arts to develop critical thinking. [5,135]

Modern teaching methods (including, of course, interactive ones) are methods of developing competencies based on the interaction of students and their involvement in the learning process, and not just on passive or reproductive perception of the material. Modern infrastructure (technical means) of training, which includes information, technological, organizational and communication components, allowing for the effective use of the advantages of, say, distance learning. [6,22]

Results: As mentioned earlier, Azerbaijan is currently pursuing a state policy that covers these aspects, focusing on transforming intellectual capital into economic potential. In the globalized world, research into the foundations of economic breakthroughs in developed countries shows that the application of scientific innovations plays a key role in this development.

Today, education cannot be imagined without science. In developed countries, universities are primarily structured as centers of scientific research, and the educational process is based on scientific innovations. Thus, universities evolve into centers of science and education, meeting the needs of society. Universities in our country must also fulfill this mission. However, strengthening the material-technical base of the educational system, equipping institutions with modern technical equipment, and acquiring cutting-edge devices are not easy tasks.

This article discusses the innovative aspects of the development of technological education in the context of information changes in society and education. The use of high technologies as a tool for transmitting information and developing modern technological processes is shown to enable the optimization of the teaching process and enhance its efficiency. [7]

The article explores the impact of high-intellectual technologies on pedagogical methods, as well as how they foster creative and logical thinking skills and enhance interpersonal communication abilities. These aspects are particularly relevant in the context of modernizing education in Azerbaijan. To identify the structure and determinants of social communication based on the specifics of pedagogical activity, the main research directions are analyzed. [12]

This day, specialists are in a position where information and communication are forcing them to perform various roles. This fundamentally changes the situation and objectives of education, particularly technological education, because it requires mastering the most promising technologies that provide high quality and low production costs to meet market demands. It is well-known that the term "technology" refers to methods of transforming raw materials, materials, and the characteristics and form of production processes, interpreted alongside skills and craftsmanship. [8]

Technological education is aimed at mastering the culture of human interaction with machinery, equipment, and energy systems. An important aspect of this is the interaction between humans and machines, equipment, and energy devices. Computer systems and technology have been widely applied in machine control systems. The discovery and development of new technologies are significant sources for improving university curricula. [7,] The innovative aspect of this direction is the introduction of new teaching methods and materials into the curriculum, which has the following benefits:

- it increases students' interest in new technologies.
- it enhances focus on different methods of presenting educational materials.
- it allows the presentation of specific aspects of a process through the use of new technologies.

The challenges of the 21st century demand that each of us acquire new abilities, skills, and knowledge, enabling effective performance.

Discussion and Conclusion: Today, the main task is to prepare society to "adopt" scientific innovations and ensure they are effectively utilized, which requires global collaboration, not just within one country. Without familiarizing ourselves with modern innovations and acquiring practical experience with them, talent, strong theoretical knowledge, a good memory, and intellectual capacity are not enough.

Therefore, we must focus on integrating and cooperating between universities worldwide, so that young people are introduced to scientific innovations during their education. It is important to note that high technologies widely used in scientific research and production bring new perspectives to pedagogical technologies. The development of computer technology and the Internet has altered our understanding of data transmission technologies, which, alongside the application of high technologies in teaching, requires adjustments in communication technologies.[7]

Innovative teaching methods are not just the introduction of advanced technologies or following the latest trends, but a complete educational methodology based on new teaching strategies that focus on the needs and characteristics of students. [8] These methods allow students to be actively involved in the learning process and encourage interaction with classmates and the teacher. This means a lot of work on the part of students, but unlike traditional teaching, which focuses on the volume of knowledge transferred, innovative methods allow us to understand what students actually learned in the classroom. Many teachers are already using innovative teaching strategies to increase student engagement.[9,215]

Here are 7 benefits of innovative teaching methods that make them worth trying.

1. Encourage inquiry – these methods encourage inquiry and broaden one's horizons

2. Improve critical thinking and problem-solving skills – students can progress at their own pace and find new ways to solve problems instead of looking for a ready-made answer in a textbook.

3. Information Dosing – Teachers still give students new information, but now they break it down into smaller parts, which increases the speed and quality of assimilation of the material.

4. Acquiring Social Competencies – Students now require more complex tools in the classroom to help them develop their creative potential. And when completing individual or group projects, they learn to plan their time, set priorities, communicate, and work in a team.

5. Checking the assimilation of the material – grades and exams can say a lot about the abilities and knowledge of the student, but not everything (especially if you cheat!). Innovative methods allow you to better control the process, understand and solve students' problems.

6. Increased self-esteem – the use of innovative methods will allow students to understand what they have learned and what they still need to master. This

will help make learning more conscious and increase motivation.

7. Vivid lessons – avoid teacher monologues or awkward pauses – with innovative methods, students are actively speaking out in class.

Nowadays Virtual reality technologies open a window into the real world right in the classroom and allow students to interact with "real" objects instead of flat images on a screen.

The most important, extremely necessary stage in the work on innovation.

is its testing and experiment to check its reliability and efficiency. It is this stage that allows us to identify the "pain points" of the innovation, the risk points. The more negative factors that the innovation being developed carries are identified, the fewer problems there will be in the future when using it.

At the same time, developers, having identified the negative aspects of the innovation, make certain changes and adjustments. Only after this can innovation be implemented. Over time, innovation becomes a tradition, then it comes into conflict with modernity, and the cycle repeats. In education, along with medicine, it is very important to achieve minimal negative impact of innovations. Scientific and technical innovations are essential to the transformation of modern education. When effectively implemented, they can bridge learning gaps, personalize education, and enhance student outcomes. [11]

However, to realize these benefits, education systems must address issues of access, ethics, and support structures. As we move into a new era of digital learning, a balance between innovation and equity will be the key to long-term success. [10]

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References:

1. Aksarina Ya. S. Research of the problems of innovative pedagogical activity in the system of modern professional education / Bulletin of the Yugra State University 2015. Issue 1 (36). p. 17–19

2. Andreeva A.V. Features of scientific and innovative activities in the education system // Modern problems of science and education–2014 №2 ISSN 2070-7428 "Перечень" ВАК ИФ РИНЦ = 1,006 ISSN 2070-7428 "List" VAK IF RINTS =1.006

3. Slobodchikov V.I. Problems of formation and development of innovative education. / Innovations in education, 2003, No. 2. p. 4 – 28

4. Downton, M. P. (2018). Preparation for future teaching: Authentic activities in a teacher education classroom. In D. Polly, M. Putman, T. Petty, & A. Good (Eds.), *Innovative practices in teacher preparation and graduate-level teacher education programs* (pp. 293–305). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-3068-8.ch016>

5. Fuad, D. R. S. M., Musa, K., & Hashim, Z. (2020). Innovation culture in education: A systematic review of the literature. *Management in Education*,

36(3), 135–149.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0892020620959760>

6. Grevtseva G.Ya., Shvachko E.V., Osipova T.V. Innovation as a Pedagogical Category: Essence and Features / Bulletin of SUSU. Series "Educational Sciences". 23, 2019. Vol. 11, No. 1. Pp. 21–26 2014. – No. 2.; URL: <https://science-education.ru/ru/article/view?id=12628> (date of access: 04.04.2023)

7. Howard, S. K., Schrum, L., Voogt, J., & Sligte, H. (2021). Designing research to inform sustainability and scalability of digital technology innovations. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 69, 2309–2329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09913-y>

8. Ilyin G.L. *Innovations in Education*. Textbook. Prometheus Publishing House, 2015

9. Kotyk, T., Romanyuk, S., Bogush, A., Rudenko, Y., & Nepomniashcha, I. (2021). Innovative and project activities of future education. *Laplace em Revista (International)*, 7(3B), 213–219.

10. Nicholls A. *Managing Educational Innovations*. London, 1983.

11. Rubalcaba L. *Understanding Innovation in Education: A Service CoProduction Perspective* by Luis Rubalcaba. Department of Economics and Business Administration, University of Alcala, 28802 Alcala de Henares, Spain *Economies* 2022, 10(5), 96; Электронный ресурс <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies10050096>

12. Valiyeva Z. Using innovative methods in education. *Education Scientific-pedagogical, publisistic journal*. 15.10.2021 <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202016610010><https://t.ehsiljurnali.az/>